

Paradiplomacy in India: Expanding State's Influence in International Relations

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Abstract

With India's growing economic might, the nation's influence in the global landscape is visible. The important point to note is that it is not the only effort of the government in New Delhi, other actors are also playing a crucial role. Indian culture, industries, educational institutions, space institutions etc. are also the ones to credit. Each state of the union or to say city is bringing something to the table and representing India as a whole. Like Mumbai by hosting international financial institutions and events like the Mumbai International Film Festival. Hyderabad is the hub for pharmaceutical and biotech industries, attracting international collaboration. Tamil Nadu has been a significant hub for Japanese automotive companies. In this paper, we are going to analyse what role different states and non-state actors have performed in India concerning paradiplomacy and how effective it has been in achieving its desired goal. Also, see how paradiplomacy differs from diplomacy. What are the driving factors of paradiplomacy and at the same time what are the challenges?

Keywords: Paradiplomacy, Cooperation, Fdi, Modi, Centre-State Relation, Decentralisation

1. Introduction

With India's growing economic and diplomatic might, the nation's influence in the global landscape is visible. The important point to note is that it is not the only effort of the government in New Delhi, other actors are also playing a crucial role. Indian culture, industries, educational institutions, space institutions etc. are also the ones to credit. Each state of the union or to say city is bringing something to the table and representing India as a whole. Like Mumbai by hosting international financial institutions and events like the Mumbai International Film Festival. Hyderabad is the hub for pharmaceutical and biotech industries, attracting international collaboration. Tamil Nadu has been a significant hub for Japanese automotive companies. All this engagement of non-state actors and subnational governments in international relations is referred to as Paradiplomacy and India is evolving and applying it efficiently.

Paradiplomacy refers to the autonomous international endeavours undertaken by subnational entities, such as states, regions or cities, to advance their own economic, cultural, and political objectives, separate from the central government. This notion emphasises the growing influence of local governments in global events, propelled by the processes of globalisation and decentralisation. Paradiplomacy involves sub-national governments (states and cities) engaging in international relations and diplomacy. In the 1980s, Paradiplomacy emerged in academic literature, focusing on Canadian provinces and American states' foreign operations amid globalization and North American interconnectedness (Paquin, 2020, p. 49).

Panayotis Soldatos (1990, p. 34), the inventor of the concept, defined Paradiplomacy, as "*direct continuation, and to varying degrees, from sub-state government, foreign activities*" and also called it "*a result of a crisis at the level of the nation state's systemic process and foreign-policy performance*".

According to Stefan Wolff, Paradiplomacy is the "*foreign policy capacity of sub-state entities, their participation, independent of their metropolitan state, in the international arena in pursuit of their specific international interests*" (Tewari, 2017, p. 3).

Lecours (2008, p. 13) claims that “*paradiplomacy can serve many different purposes, including economic development, cultural diffusion, technological advancement and political affirmation.*”

Paradiplomacy has been significant on the global stage in regions like Catalonia in Spain, Quebec in Canada and various US states. Certain states have employed para-diplomatic strategies to address ethnic and cultural conflicts, such as Canada, Belgium and Spain. In contrast, Chatterji and Saha (2017, p. 391) mention that China has focused solely on economic growth and gradually extended its benefits to underdeveloped regions. India’s federal structure also allows states and cities to engage internationally, enhancing their economic and cultural profiles. The drive for using paradiplomacy to build a new India has gained momentum in recent years. In this paper, we are going to analyse what role different states and non-state actors have performed in India concerning paradiplomacy and how effective it has been in achieving its desired goal.

2. Paradiplomacy and Diplomacy

Para-diplomacy, a recently emerged institutional phenomenon in the field of international relations, has achieved worldwide recognition in Europe, North America and Asia. This process entails the establishment of different offices like of trade and culture by provinces or states in foreign countries, active participation in negotiations and fostering connections with counterparts from other nations to address a range of challenges. These connections can encompass a wide spectrum of activities, including educational exchanges, trade and investments. Sub-national entities have derived advantages from para-diplomatic operations and have increased trade and investment prospects.

The emergence and acceptance of paradiplomatic activity, as acknowledged and accepted by scholars such as Cornago (2010, p. 28), should not be perceived as a replacement for the state, but rather as a supplementary element Wolff (2007, p. 149). There is no doubt that negotiations, treaty drafting and coordination of actions are still conducted by foreign affairs ministries. Although state leaders are increasingly involved in foreign affairs, they do so from the standpoint of the central government without undermining the distinct voice of the State. Alvarez (2020) claims that the state, both as a participant and a focal point of examination, will remain crucial for comprehending the global stage.

However, Chatterji and Saha (2017, p. 378) failing to consider paradiplomatic participation impedes a more intricate examination of the global reality. Para-diplomacy encompasses several manifestations, although it is always subject to the constraints and boundaries set by the foreign policy of the republic to which the component unit is affiliated. The administration of international affairs is widely acknowledged as a fundamental component of sovereign power, both in principle and in reality.

3. Paradiplomacy at the India’s State Level

Sub-national entities have often gained significant developmental advantages from para-diplomatic efforts. Examples of this may be seen in countries like Brazil or China, where these activities have led to greater trade and investment opportunities, similar to what has been observed in the USA (Chatterji & Saha, 2017, p. 391). Several Indian states participate in paradiplomatic contacts as a means of supplementing conventional diplomacy. At the beginning of 2015, the Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) requested the Chief Minister (CM) of Andhra Pradesh, Chandrababu Naidu, to head a prominent group of representatives to China in April of the same year, which was a month before Prime Minister (PM) Narendra Modi’s official visit to China. During PM Modi’s visit to Bangladesh in June 2015, he invited Mamata Banerjee, the CM of West Bengal, to be part of his official entourage. Former PM Manmohan Singh followed a similar approach during his official visit to Bangladesh in September 2011. He invited four CMs from the northeastern states of India that share a border with Bangladesh. Tewari (2017, pp. 5–6) claims the practice of including CMs in prime ministerial travels overseas or MEA requesting a CM to lead an international delegation before a prime ministerial visit is a quite new development in India’s official foreign relations protocol.

3.1 Key States and Their Initiatives

To better understand the extent to which paradiplomacy has been accepted and what results it has produced, we will analyse some case studies in the Indian context. Some of the key states that have actively considered paradiplomacy in India are:

3.1.1 Tamil Nadu

Tamil Nadu has been actively participating in paradiplomacy. Throughout the Sri Lankan Civil War, the CMs of Tamil Nadu played a prominent role as de facto negotiators advocating for the 'Tamil cause' in Sri Lanka. The state has also participated in parliamentary resolutions about the Katchatheevu problem and the repeated apprehension of fishermen by the Sri Lankan Navy in the Palk Strait. Tamil Nadu has adopted a strong focus on trade, business, research, medical and environmental issues in its regional diplomacy. Between October 2019 and September 2023, the state attracted a total of \$9.85 billion in foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows. The 2024 edition of Tamil Nadu's Global Investors Meet (GIM) garnered investments totalling around \$81 billion and is projected to generate 2.69 million employment opportunities. With M. K. Stalin at the helm, Tamil Nadu, under his leadership as the CM, aspires to achieve the status of a \$1 trillion economy by the year 2030 (Vidya et al., 2024). CM Stalin has also actively engaged in investment-focused activities, including trips to Singapore, Spain and the World Economic Forum.

Tamil Nadu's engagement in paradiplomacy enables it to manage matters about fishing rights, reservations, remittances for refugees and human trafficking with greater prudence. In economic terms, Tamil Nadu is home to numerous prominent car manufacturers. Hyundai, Ford, Renault-Nissan and BMW have established their production operations in the state (Reports Guru, 2023). Tamil Nadu is a prominent hub for tyre manufacturing, hosting numerous large tyre companies. Chennai, the capital of Tamil Nadu, can create 1.71 million units of vehicles every year (Government of Tamil Nadu, n.d.). Chennai has been transformed into the 'Detroit of Asia' by Japan's automotive sector (Sridharan, 2019). This is due to car manufacturers capitalising on tax incentives and the development of new infrastructure. Furthermore, there has been the emergence of culinary and cultural links as a result of business connections. The Tamil Nadu Technology Development & Promotion Centre organises the yearly Conference on Automotive R&D Trends in the state (Rao, 2024). This meeting offers a vital opportunity for suppliers and Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) to navigate product advancements, decrease operational expenses, and influence profit margins.

3.1.2 Gujarat

Gujarat has been a leading proponent of paradiplomacy, exemplified by its efforts such as the Vibrant Gujarat Summit. The biennial international investor summit was launched by the former CM Narendra Modi in 2003, to establish Gujarat as a leading investment hub in India (Malhotra, 2020). Gujarat successfully engaged in city diplomacy on the world stage by luring international investors and highlighting the state's economic potential. For reference, during the Vibrant Summit series, Gujarat has seen thousands of Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) signed and billions of dollars invested. In 2003, there were 76 MoUs worth USD 14 billion, in 2005 there were 226 MoUs worth USD 20 billion, in 2007 there were 675 MoUs worth USD 152 billion, in 2009 there were 8662 MoUs worth USD 243 billion and in 2011 there were 7936 MoUs worth USD 462 billion (Prajapati, 2016, p. 1).

Gujarat organises global investor events and actively encourages foreign trade. These endeavours contribute to the practice of economic paradiplomacy, in which states utilise their economic advantages to attract foreign investment and cultivate economic connections with other nations (Ratna, 2013). Gujarat's active engagement in paradiplomacy has not only bolstered its position but also enhanced India's foreign policy framework. Gujarat demonstrates how sub-national organisations can have a significant impact on international relations by utilising their economic potential and solving regional concerns.

3.1.3 Maharashtra

During the 1990s, a combination of reasons led to the increase of paradiplomacy in India. These factors encompassed economic changes, the rapid growth of the IT industry (with South Indian states taking the lead) and the rise of influential regional leaders (Maini, 2023a). During this period, Maharashtra, being one of India's economically prominent states, played a pivotal role. At the World Economic Forum (WEF) 2022, Maharashtra entered into agreements with 23 companies, pledging to invest more than ₹30,000 crore (about \$4 billion). More than 55% of these assets consist of Foreign Direct assets (FDI) originating from countries such as Japan, Germany, and other nations (Business Today Desk, 2022). Deputy CM Devendra Fadnavis presented Maharashtra as a prime location to attract Japanese investors. He highlighted the importance of cooperation across several industries, such as infrastructure, education and health. While on his 2023 tour in Japan, Fadnavis engaged in meetings at the Indian House in Tokyo to entice Japanese companies to invest in Maharashtra (Express News Service, 2023). The state's

objective is to provide prospects for Japanese businessmen in Maharashtra, which is the foremost choice for foreign direct investment.

On the cultural diplomacy front, the efforts of Maharashtra are enhanced by its abundant cultural legacy and dynamic arts sector. The state organises cultural festivals, art exhibitions, and diplomatic interactions with foreign nations. Efforts such as promoting Marathi movies, literature and performing arts internationally contribute to the enhancement of cultural connections and the cultivation of mutual comprehension. And how could Bollywood and Bombay's relationship be forgotten? Maharashtra has also formed sister city alliances with cities across the globe. These alliances enable the exchange of cultural knowledge, foster educational cooperation and facilitate collaborative projects. For example, Mumbai has established sister city relationships with cities such as Shanghai, Los Angeles and Yokohama.

Maharashtra and Singapore engage in cooperation in various domains such as smart cities, logistics and finance. Singaporean firms have made investments in the infrastructure projects of the state. South Korean corporations have successfully built a strong foothold in Maharashtra, namely in the automobile and electronics industries. Collaborations primarily emphasise the transfer of technology and the development of skills. Germany and Maharashtra engage in collaboration in various domains, including automotive production, technology and research. German corporations have made investments in the state, so contributing to its economic expansion. The states of Maharashtra and Israel have formed a partnership in the fields of agriculture, water management and innovation. This relationship has facilitated the implementation of initiatives such as drip irrigation and agrotech.

3.2 Some other states engaged in paradiplomacy

India's chairmanship of G20 in 2023 provides the states with the chance to demonstrate not just their financial prowess but also their capacity as tourist destinations. Various regions in India have successfully hosted events, leading to significant improvements in the infrastructure of these cities. The state governments have played an active role in ensuring the success of these events, resulting in increased knowledge about diverse parts of India. Jammu and Kashmir has got the global limelight at the advent of G20. If we talk of other domains, we have to look at Odisha, which successfully hosted the International Hockey Federation's Men's Hockey World Cup in 2023, following its previous hosting of the 2018 Men's Hockey World Cup (Narayan, 2023). This demonstrates Odisha's ongoing efforts to establish itself as a prominent sports destination.

States are forming special departments and authorities to increase their global outreach. Many steps have been taken by the different governments on their own. One of the key examples is that Telangana has a specialised department that focuses on overseas outreach. In 2021, Kerala designated Venu Rajamony, a former diplomat, as an officer assigned to the Kerala government for overseas cooperation (PTI, 2021). Various CMs, such as Pinari Vijayan of Kerala, MK Stalin of Tamil Nadu and Manohar Lal Khattar of Haryana, have made visits to the UAE. As a result, the UAE has recognised the significance of India's state governments on multiple occasions. Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, Uttar Pradesh (UP) and Nepal engaged in collaboration by exchanging information, coordinating their efforts and procuring medical supplies (PTI, 2023a). UP has an extensive border with Nepal. UP, being an adjacent state, plays a pivotal role in the diplomatic ties between India and Nepal. UP's perspectives and concerns are given careful attention in discussions about water resources, land boundary difficulties and other bilateral issues.

Indian states are also actively pursuing opportunities to establish connections with other countries through educational collaborations and knowledge exchange. Rajasthan established the Centre for Excellence in Tourism Training at Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, Udaipur, with support from Singapore (ANI, 2016). In February 2023, Punjab dispatched 36 principals to Singapore for training (Dasgupta, 2023). The Punjab government has signed a MoU with the British Council Education India Pvt Limited (BCEIPL) to offer a specialised English language course aimed at improving the professional abilities of students, with a particular focus on the industrial and services sector (PTI, 2023b).

4. Drivers of Paradiplomacy in India

India's paradiplomacy has been propelled by economic reforms, technical developments, robust regional leadership and the shifting global scene. As nations persist in asserting their interests on the global stage, paradiplomacy remains a crucial component of India's foreign policy framework. Some of the major drivers of paradiplomacy are:

4.1 Political Factors

India possesses a democratic system with a theoretically federal constitution. This constitution mandates that state governments are elected by the people, but they do not possess any jurisdiction in matters related to international affairs. Despite the absence of a constitutional provision or institutional framework to address centre-state disagreements on foreign policy matters, Indian states have emerged as more and more influential participants in global affairs. One of the reasons for the increased significance of state-level politics, as claimed by Sharma et al. (2020, p. 567) is the establishment of '*regionalized coalition governments*' at the centre since 1996.

The emergence of strong regional leaders played a crucial role in promoting paradiplomacy. Leaders who championed their state's interests on the national and international stage contributed to the visibility and influence of their respective states. Their proactive engagement helped shape foreign policy narratives beyond the central government. A successful example is Narendra Modi, who actively pursued subnational diplomacy during his tenure as the CM of Gujarat. In August 2003, Modi advocated for the Vibrant Gujarat summit in London and delivered a speech at a highly attended rally held at the Wembley Conference Centre. His international journeys as CM received formal acknowledgement and were mostly centred on economic matters. He travelled to China in 2006 and 2011, Singapore in 2006 and Japan in 2012 (Wyatt, 2017, p. 116). These travels provided Modi with an opportunity to demonstrate his keenness for economic development and foster a perception of his proficiency in economic matters.

Chandrababu Naidu as CM strongly dedicated to advancing the interests of Andhra Pradesh through frequent international trips and dynamic public relations efforts. Yogi Adityanath, UP's CM, has also endeavoured to allure investment and foster tourism. The government has orchestrated events such as the Kumbh Mela, which attract international attention. The government led by Pinarayi Vijayan has been actively involved in international diplomacy. The Kerala diaspora plays a key role in strengthening relations with other nations. The state prioritises the global promotion of the tourist, healthcare, and education industries.

In October 2014, the Modi government established a state division under the Ministry of External Affairs. This division aims to enhance productive communication between Indian state governments and foreign nations. PM Modi has consistently emphasised the importance of 'cooperative federalism' in the realm of foreign policy. In 2015, PM Modi visited China and a conference for state-province leaders was also established in that (Maini, 2023b). Both at the state and centre level work is being conducted to improve paradiplomacy and benefit as much as the states could on their own. This centre-state cooperation in paradiplomacy has proved to be another example of decentralisation in India.

4.2 Economic Incentives

The implementation of economic liberalisation policies in 1991 created new avenues for states to participate in international engagement. With India's integration into the global economy, states acknowledged the imperative of engaging in international affairs to allure foreign investment, stimulate commerce and cultivate economic expansion. The concurrent processes of globalisation and liberalisation have had a profound impact on the state governments in India. During the period spanning from the late 1990s to the early 2000s, the information technology (IT) industry experienced substantial expansion, with South Indian states such as Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Maharashtra taking the lead. These states utilised their expertise in IT to actively interact with international investors, forge technology alliances and globally market their regions.

The wider global framework of liberalisation, democratisation and globalisation enabled subnational governments to engage in international activities. With the decrease in barriers to communication and travel, nations discovered it became simpler to cooperate with foreign counterparts, establish sister-city connections, and engage in international forums. Many states are organizing international investor summits to attract foreign investment. One such example is the Uttar Pradesh Global Investors Summit 2023. The UP government has declared that a total of 18,000 agreements, amounting to an investment of ₹32.92 lakh crore, were inked at the summit. Surprisingly, this investment intention exceeds the Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) of UP. Andhra Pradesh announced that it has received 340 investment proposals totalling around ₹13 lakh crore, which is a little less than the GSDP of the state. Karnataka said that Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) with a total investment above ₹9.8 lakh crore has been signed. In April 2022, Assam in the northeastern region garnered significant attention by attracting investment proposals totalling more than ₹87,000 crore. In July 2022, Tamil Nadu announced the signing of 60 MoUs valued at ₹1.25 lakh crore. In August, Rajasthan declared MoUs amounting to investments of ₹70,000 crore. Meanwhile, Maharashtra introduced offshore innovation and entered into MoUs worth ₹1.37 lakh crore at the World

Economic Forum (Aiyar, 2023). The final amount invested on the ground is a matter of debate but these data are enough to show how the economic interests have garnered the state's interest in paradiplomacy.

4.3 Cultural and Social Factors

India's cultural exchange programs promote artistic expression, foster global friendships and celebrate the rich heritage of its states. In 2022, Cultural Exchange Programmes were established with nations including Turkmenistan, Panama, Denmark, Senegal, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Romania, to enhance bilateral cultural interaction. Indian ministers actively engaged in international cultural forums, such as the 19th Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) Culture Ministers Meeting and the 7th BRICS Culture Ministers' Meeting. The primary objective of the National Cultural Exchange Programme (NCEP) is to propagate Indian art and culture in hitherto unexplored regions and foster cultural ties between India and other nations. The process entails the signing of bilateral Cultural Agreements and the organisation of Cultural Exchange Programmes. A total of 229 Cultural Societies across 35 Indian Missions abroad were allocated roughly ₹666.72 lakhs for the financial year 2022-23 (Ministry of Culture, 2022).

Paradiplomacy is significantly influenced by subnational identity politics. The importance of this matter can have far-reaching implications, even to the extent of impacting the diplomatic relations of a country. This can be observed in the competition among political factions in Tamil Nadu to demonstrate their backing for the Tamil minority in Sri Lanka (Sharma et al., 2020, pp. 587–588). Tamil Nadu has significant cultural and historical connections with Sri Lanka, primarily because of the presence of the Tamil ethnic group. Kerala, renowned for its substantial expatriate community in Gulf nations, has successfully employed paradiplomacy. The state government engages in cooperation with Gulf states with matters about labour migration, remittances and economic collaboration. The citizens of Kerala who work in the Gulf region play a crucial role in enhancing these connections. The Telugu-speaking population in the United States has actively engaged in paradiplomacy. Their engagement encompasses a wide range of activities, including cultural events, economic collaborations and educational exchanges, all of which contribute to the enhancement of India-US relations. The Punjabi diaspora in Canada has played a crucial role in advancing India's interests and ideals. High-profile trips, such as the visit of Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau to Punjab, emphasise the increasing influence of the diaspora in shaping bilateral relations (Maini, 2023a).

5. Challenges in the space of Paradiplomacy

Paradiplomacy, which refers to the involvement of regional or local entities in international affairs, also serves as a versatile means to advance their interests and assert their identity (Lecours, 2008). Nevertheless, Dickson (2017, p. iv) contends that it also presents difficulties, especially when sub-national governments with robust regional identities partake in paradiplomatic endeavours, potentially undermining the supremacy of the central state. This issue is further exacerbated by the ambiguity surrounding the jurisdiction to engage in global diplomacy and many raised the possibility of separatist factions seeking international backing however Novialdi et al. (2021, p. 6253) found that there is no space for separatist factions to gather international support through paradiplomacy. Referring to India, Lecours (2008, p. 14) asserts that states may not necessarily adopt paradiplomacy, especially when it comes from groups that express a distinct identity or have nationalist aspirations, as it strengthens the idea of national unity. Referring to India, Lecours (2008, p. 14) asserts that states may not necessarily adopt paradiplomacy, especially when it comes from groups that express a distinct identity or have nationalist aspirations, as it strengthens the idea of national unity. In this particular setting, he asserts that paradiplomacy has the potential to create conflicts, making intergovernmental ties particularly crucial.

In their 2021 review, Novialdi et al. (2021, p. 6265) examined 30 research publications on diplomacy and identified several unresolved issues concerning the institutions responsible for conducting international relations in the context of paradiplomacy. They found that institutions had a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of paradiplomacy. Furthermore, the province and city authorities have not yet comprehended the concept and implementation of paradiplomacy. The provinces and cities were awaiting orders from the central government about international cooperation. Furthermore, paradiplomacy is believed to be a strategic approach employed by the province to garner assistance from international entities to establish legal status and get international acknowledgement. The central government held the utmost authority and was responsible for overseeing the paradiplomacy activities conducted by each province of the country.

Brian Hocking believes the notion of paradiplomacy was developed to strengthen the differentiation between the government in power at the centre and sub-national governments, hence intensifying conflicts between the two

levels of government (Paquin, 2020, p. 50). India, as a novice in para-diplomacy, has limited experience due to its multiparty and electoral system, societal pluralism, federal political structure and diverse parties running the central and state governments. Chatterji and Saha (2017, p. 391) claim that the central government may have reservations about the possible benefits and drawbacks of promoting para-diplomatic activism at the sub-national level.

Chatterji and Saha (2017, p. 382) assert confidently that granting a group with a unique ethnic or cultural identity the opportunity to engage in para-diplomacy through autonomous representation might potentially lead to heightened ethnic mobilisation and internal conflict in a culturally varied society. Indeed, this could undermine the cohesion of the state. In a pluralistic society like India, if unchecked or unregulated, this could lead to serious implications. Paradiplomacy presents advantageous prospects for India, but it necessitates meticulous handling to prevent unforeseen repercussions. Ensuring a harmonious equilibrium between central government control and sub-national efforts is a crucial undertaking in India's ever-changing foreign policy environment. In India, it has been shown that the interests and abilities of subnational units, along with individual leadership, impact the extent to which governments engage in paradiplomacy. In this regard, Sharma et al. (2020, p. 588) claim only a handful of Indian states, namely Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Madhya Pradesh exhibit significant levels of activity.

6. Policy Implications

Para-diplomacy aligns with decentralisation, thereby promoting democratisation. It fosters a greater connection between diplomatic procedures and the general public, increasing people's engagement, knowledge and participation in foreign policy. Undoubtedly, the willingness of the constituent units to participate in para-diplomacy will be contingent upon their level of interest and their ability to effectively manage it. That's the reason Chatterji and Saha (2017, pp. 381-382) mentioned that the problem of competence is crucial when considering developing countries in Asia and Africa.

States in India which are governed by political parties associated with those in power at the centre adhere to the foreign policy position of the central government. In contrast, states that are not linked with any one group, especially those in opposition, often adopt confrontational stances on contentious matters and receive less assistance from the central authority (Sharma et al., 2020, p. 587). Since 2014, the National Democratic Alliance has been at the centre and the Bhartiya Janta Party and alliances have government in many states. Thus, the paradiplomacy has gained momentum due to this same party governance in the states and at the centre.

7. Conclusion

States and cities in India are increasingly engaging in Paradiplomacy, with significant economic and cultural benefits. That is evident from the analysis made above. Although some states are at the forefront, others are catching them fast. States are coming up with their unique identity and representing them at the global level. Programmes like One District One Product of UP can be effective in promoting local products globally. The overall cooperation of the centre and states is necessary in today's globalised world despite their political differences. Strengthening Paradiplomacy can enhance India's global influence and regional development. Chatterji and Saha (2017, p. 392) claimed that the majority of states in India exhibit a lack of willingness or ability to engage in meaningful discussions with consular personnel from foreign nations who are interested in facilitating investments. However, in this analysis, it was found that this was not the case today. Many Indian states, such as Gujrat, Maharashtra, Kerala etc., are actively engaging with foreign partners and promoting their economic and cultural fronts.

The participation of states is not at its best but as mentioned above paradiplomacy is still in its infancy. It will need some time to fully evolve in pluralistic societies like India. Lecours (2008, p. 13) mentioned the establishment of paradiplomacy inevitably requires domestic adaptations and the study found that India is adopting. The paradiplomacy is promoted at both the central and state levels. There are many factors for that, like the increasing role of technology in enhancing paradiplomatic efforts. Better coordination between central and state governments can streamline efforts. There is an urgent need for training and resources for state officials to handle international relations effectively and both the central and state governments should collaborate on that. As said paradiplomacy is still evolving there is a need for more empirical studies on the outcomes of paradiplomacy in India. Apart from economic and cultural considerations, a focus on sustainable development and climate diplomacy is also crucial in today's world for a peaceful and secure future.

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